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Work Package 3
Formalise Knowledge on population-level exposure assessment

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the continuously expanding, comprehensive exposure assessment over time in a population-based collection of cytological/nucleic acid samples from multiple anatomical sites and serum samples from two randomised screening cohorts of over 15.000 1992-97 born women. The women received or refused prophylactic human papillomavirus vaccination as early adolescents in 2007-2010 and have attended randomised cervical screening every third year since 2014. Based on informed consent, the serial samples are available for high-throughput laboratory analyses on the extent of sexually transmitted infection (STI) exposures and their sequelae in fertile-aged Finnish females as population standardised prevalence, incidence and cumulative incidence rate ratios for up to 15 years.

The Finnish HPV Vaccine Cohort (F-VAC) is comprised of the two largest randomised human papillomavirus (HPV) intervention cohorts, which originated from overlapping sources. The first is a community randomised phase IV trial assessing the impact of girls-only or gender-neutral HPV vaccination strategies. The second and overlapping is a set of two individually randomised trials examining the frequency of cervical screening in HPV-vaccinated and unvaccinated women. In 2007, 80,272 early adolescents aged 12 to 15 were invited to participate in the phase IV trial across 33 Finnish towns. Of the 39,420 girls, 20,514 participated, and 12,402 received three doses of HPV16/18 vaccine between 2007 and 2010. From 2010 to 2014, 2,298 adolescent females received HPV16/18 vaccination at age 18 during the first follow-up visit. This group stemmed from originally hepatitis B-virus (HBV) vaccinated 3,572 early adolescents and 1,836 unvaccinated similarly-aged females

Simultaneously, an overlapping 2014 individually randomised trial assessed the accuracy of infrequent vs. frequent screening of HPV-vaccinated women. Three additional follow-up visits with cervical and blood sampling occurred at ages 22 (6,959 participants), 25 (6,381 participants), and 28 (over 4,489 participants). In addition, 1,258 unvaccinated women who originally refused or were too young to participate in the community-randomized HPV vaccination trial or Finnish national HPV vaccination program have participated in a parallel randomised trial on frequent vs. infrequent screening of herd effect protected women.

Participation in the phase IV trial required parental consent, while participation in the cervical screening trial and subsequent follow-up visits required informed consent. The F-VAC includes demographic information, residential and vaccination history, comprehensive sexually transmitted infection status (not HIV) at DNA and/or serology levels, cervical cytology and histology data, and smoking habits (at ages 25 and 28). The use of this population-wide HPV vaccination data follows the regulations outlined in the Finnish Biobank Act §§26 & 27 and is governed by the Findata instructions for data protection and security (www.findata.fi).

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Introduction

Deliverable 3.3 comprises documentation demonstrating the continuously expanding, comprehensive, population-level exposure assessment over time based on high-throughput laboratory analyses of the consecutive longitudinal sample set from Finland for evaluating the extent of sexually transmitted human papillomavirus (HPV) infections as a cumulative, calendar-time- and age-stratified exposure(s) of the target population for up to 15 years (Lehtinen et al., 2015; Vänskä et al, 2020; Pimenoff et al., 2023).

The HPV vaccination cohort study is unique in its scope and scale, and it provides a wealth of data on the real-world effectiveness of the HPV vaccine at the Finnish population level. The cohort data have already been used for several groundbreaking papers, including studies on the impact of different (gender-neutral vs. girls-only) vaccination strategies at the population level on HPV prevalence (Lehtinen et al. 2018a, 2018b, Vänskä et al. 2020; Gray et al. 2021), HPV-vaccine's impact on HPV-associated cancer incidence (Luostarinen et al. 2018), vaccine safety (Lehtinen et al. 2016, Bi et al. 2019) and the effect of HPV vaccination strategies on the epidemiology (Gray et al. 2018, 2019, 2020) and ecology of oncogenic HPVs (Pimenoff et al., 2023).

The findings of the Finnish HPV vaccination cohort have had a significant impact on global public health policy on HPV vaccination (Lehtinen et al. 2019, 2022, Lehtinen & Pimenoff 2022, Lehtinen et al. 2023a) and screening (Louvanto et al., 2020; Lehtinen & Pimenoff, 2022, Lehtinen et al., 2023b). The cohorts have also served as a model for other large-scale vaccination studies. Here, we will offer some vistas on using the established cohort to understand the long-term effects of HPV exposure and the impact of HPV vaccination at the population level.

Cohort dataset

3.3.1 The Finnish HPV Vaccination Cohort (F-VAC)

The current widespread implementation of the human papillomavirus vaccine is fundamentally altering the global dynamics of the virus-host interaction. Substantial proportions of adolescent and early adult birth cohorts now possess durable vaccine-induced immunity against various prevalent HPV genotypes. Additionally, the varying herd effects from girls-only and gender-neutral vaccination prove differential effectiveness in preventing infections among unvaccinated adolescents and young adults (Vänskä et al. 2020; Gray et al. 2021). This transformative phase in the ongoing interplay between persistent HPV infection and host populations necessitates vigilant monitoring of vaccine-induced evolutionary responses, including potential type-replacement within the HPV ecology.

The impact of HPV vaccination programs suggests imminent alterations in HPV type distribution related to cervical infections, precancer and screening (Lehtinen et al. 2023b). However, these observations have yet to be systematically confirmed or tested at the ecological diversity level in randomised implementation studies. Evolutionary changes in infectious agents are significantly influenced by shifts in ecological opportunities over time. Key drivers in these dynamics include specific characteristics of the host environment, such as vaccine-induced niche availability for remaining infections and pathogen antigenic variation, often prompted by the diversifying selection of the host immune system.

Here, we demonstrate the use case of F-VAC to assess the community-level occurrence of genital HPV types for up to eight years after achieving moderate (up to 50%) coverage through either girls-only or gender-neutral vaccination. Unlike previous analyses limited to pairwise HPV comparisons, we employed a generalised linear model framework and ecological diversity indices (Pimenoff et al. 2023).

Our approach also assessed how the ecological perspective unveils the modified landscape resulting from the combination of HPV vaccination and screening. A critical concern is the potential challenge posed when the prevalence of highly oncogenic HPV types is abruptly changed by vaccination, leading to a situation where even the best screening tests struggle to distinguish between true and false positive pre-cancer cases. Understanding the formation of the newly established distribution of the remaining HPV types following different vaccination strategies is crucial in this context.

Over the course of up to fifteen years of Finnish national HPV vaccination implementation, a comprehensive examination is possible to detect potential signs of evolutionary responses in non-vaccine-targeted HPV types, such as type replacement, within the established ecological niche of HPVs.

Our previous work has documented on eradicating vaccine-targeted HPVs, demonstrating rapid clearance of high oncogenicity vaccine-targeted HPV types under gender-neutral intervention (Vänskä et al. 2020; Gray et al. 2021).

Although we reported using the cohort data a decrease in vaccine-targeted HPVs at the individual level up to twelve years post-vaccination and observed prevalence fluctuations in certain non-vaccine-targeted oncogenic HPVs (i.e., HPV types 39/51/66/68/73), no consistent type-specific epidemiological evidence was found for type replacement using either HPV DNA or serology (Gray et al. 2018, 2019, 2020). Our previous modelling study suggested that the follow-up time of up to ten years in epidemiological studies might be too short to detect type replacement (Man et al. 2020). In our current analysis, however, we found evidence that suggests HPV type replacement in the community-randomized trial conducted in an HPV vaccine-naïve population (Pimenoff et al. 2023).

Here, we present data showing significant changes in the overall ecological diversity of circulating oncogenic vaccine-targeted and non-targeted HPVs in gender-neutral vaccinated communities, representing the earliest signs of niche occupation by sustaining HPVs (Pimenoff et al. 2023). The comprehensive evaluation of HPV ecological diversity, especially lower oncogenicity non-vaccine-targeted HPV types, using community-randomized HPV vaccine trial data, extensive diversity inference, and modelling consistently supports these findings. Significant changes in oncogenic HPV type diversity distribution were observed within and between communities already four to eight years post-vaccination (Pimenoff et al. 2023).

At the age of 22, eight years post-vaccination, gender-neutral vaccination communities exhibited sustained clearance of all high oncogenicity vaccine-targeted or cross-protected HPV types, notably also for HPV45 (Pimenoff et al. 2023). Additionally, there was a significant increase in α -diversity and a significant deviation in β -diversity for the sustaining HPV types compared to the girls-only vaccination communities. Importantly, despite the sustained clearance of vaccine-targeted HPV types, the gender-neutral vaccination communities returned to a similar level of HPV types α -diversity as observed for the control communities between four and eight years post-vaccination.

Our findings align with previous research indicating that the overall prevalence of oncogenic HPVs is sustained in a population, irrespective of the vaccination strategy (Louvanto et al. 2020). The rebounded total prevalence and ecological diversity of oncogenic HPVs post-vaccination also suggest sustained diversifying evolutionary forces affecting the remaining HPV strains (Pimenoff et al. 2023). However,

the long-term impact of HPV vaccination on the antigenic variation and potential virulence shifts of the remaining oncogenic HPVs remains unknown.

Using our randomised trial data on the effectiveness of HPV vaccination strategies also against HPV16 (Lehtinen et al. 2018a, 2018b, Vänskä et al. 2020, Gray et al. 2021) we highlighted (Lehtinen et al. 2023) the necessity of opting for gender-neutral HPV vaccination strategies to realistically achieve the WHO's targeted eradication of oncogenic HPVs. To effectively control oncogenic HPVs and associated cancers, it is crucial to comprehend the evolutionary dynamics of these oncoviruses, particularly under the prolonged selective pressure induced by vaccines. In communities with HPV vaccination, this change primarily arises from a decrease in the occurrence of high oncogenicity vaccine-targeted HPV types (Lehtinen et al. 2019, 2022). While the eradication of HPV16/18/31/45 is expected to eliminate the majority of cervical cancers, there is a potential concern that an increase in HPV33/35/51/52/56/66 or similar types with heightened virulence could pose a risk of HPV-related cancers in the future.

This continuously expanding, population-level exposure cohort data enables comprehensive studies on imminent threats, including the variations in transmissibility, antigenic variation, and oncogenic potential of the remaining HPV types within the newly established HPV type distribution in vaccinated populations. In this context, it is very important that the initial community-wise randomisation enables studies on the resilience of different vaccination strategies against these threats. This lays the foundation for future cancer screening efforts among HPV-vaccine recipients and the herd-effect protected non-HPV vaccinated individuals.

Summary

Here, we describe the continuously expanding, comprehensive, population-level exposure assessment over time based on high-throughput laboratory analyses of the consecutive longitudinal sample set from Finland for evaluating the extent of sexually transmitted infections, most notably different HPV types exposure as a cumulative, calendar-time- and age-dependent exposure(s) of the population for up to 15 years.

The Finnish F-VAC trial and follow-up consist of serial cervical HPV and *Chlamydia trachomatis* results and metadata among 6958 women from the 20,513 initially consented at 12-15-22-25-28 years of age and further screened for genital and oropharyngeal HPV infections, and genital *C. trachomatis* infection. Following the European GDPR, the cohort is approved for research by the Finnish Medical District Ethical Review Board, and the anonymised metadata with HPV, *C. trachomatis* and cancer association information is available in the CSC Fairdata platform through GDPR-compatible research request to the data controller in Finland.

This continuously expanding, population-level exposure cohort data enables comprehensive studies on imminent exposure threats, including the variations in transmissibility, antigenic variation, and oncogenic potential of the remaining HPV types within the newly established HPV type distribution in vaccinated populations. In this context, it is very important that the initial community-wise randomisation enables studies on the resilience of different vaccination strategies against these threats. This lays the foundation for future cancer screening efforts among HPV-vaccine recipients and the herd-effect protected non-HPV vaccinated individuals.

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